

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Impact of reduced tillage on the environmental costs of organic wheat production in Finland

Moldboard plowing, a common practice for weed control, has a direct impact on soil health and biodiversity. In this context, it is important to identify practices that balance economic efficiency and environmental protection. This study analyzes the effect of minimum tillage on environmental costs in terms of economic profitability (€ environmental impacts per € of gross margin for farmers). The main objective is to determine whether minimum tillage provides environmental benefits without compromising the profitability of organic wheat cultivation in Finland. The results provide key information for both farmers and policymakers on sustainable agricultural practices.

An environmental cost-benefit assessment (e-CBA) based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was applied to compare,

in monetary terms, two strategies: (1) control, traditional moldboard plowing and (2) reduced tillage. The results indicate that the environmental costs of both strategies are almost identical: 0.3138 €/€ (T1) and 0.3140 €/€ (T2). Besides, the main impact categories (fine particulate matter, global warming, marine eutrophication, acidification, and non-carcinogenic toxicity) are similarly distributed.

We can conclude that, from an e-CBA perspective, minimum tillage has a similar environmental impact per euro generated regarding conventional practices (i.e. for the LCA impact categories). The choice between both methods should be based on other factors, such as soil health or biodiversity.

1. Environmental costs (€ impact per € gross margin for the farmer) for each practice tested.

2. Percentage of impact categories responsible for the environmental costs calculated in each of the tested practices.

KEYWORDS

Environmental costs, impacts, minimum tillage, moldboard plowing, organic wheat cultivation.

AUTHORSHIP

Miguel Rodríguez Méndez, GEN group, ECOBAS, Universidade de Vigo, Spain

Marina Gómez Rodríguez, GEN group, ECOBAS, Universidade de Vigo, Spain

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